

AN INTEGRATED WILDFIRE RISK MANAGEMENT STRATEGY FOR THE EU: DEVELOPING RESILIENT LANDSCAPES AND SAFER COMMUNITIES

Worsening Wildfire Challenges in Europe

Wildfires have become an increasingly severe global challenge, with climate change significantly altering their frequency, timing, and locations. The 2022 as well as the recent 2025 fire seasons dramatically show the increase in area burnt and the challenges related to simultaneous fires overwhelming response capacities. While fire is a natural ecological process, the extension of fire seasons and the emergence of wildfires in previously less affected areas have raised alarm. In Europe, the Southern regions are having more intense wildfires, while in Central and Northern regions, larger areas are being impacted. This shift necessitates a coordinated European response to adapt to changing wildfire patterns.

The **drivers of wildfire risk in Europe** are complex, intertwining climate change with socio-economic shifts, such as rural abandonment and insufficient land management practices. These factors have led to unmanaged landscapes, increased fuel loads, and a decline in traditional agricultural methods. As a result, various European policies—including the EU Forest Strategy, the Bioeconomy Strategy, or the Nature Restoration Law—must align to effectively address wildfire risks in an integrated way. Governance challenges further complicate risk management, with fragmented and sometimes contradictory approaches across regions and inadequate coordination among stakeholders. Ongoing discussions between nature conservationists and supporters of landscape management depict that exemplarily.

The **impacts of wildfires** extend beyond environmental damage; they also threaten public health, safety, social justice and economic stability. Recent catastrophic events, such as the megafires in Greece and Portugal, illustrate the direct and indirect consequences of wildfires, including loss of life, health issues from smoke exposure, and significant economic costs associated with fire suppression and recovery. These wildfires also degrade carbon sinks, exacerbating climate change, and contribute to further rural abandonment.

As wildfire risk continues to rise, a comprehensive **Integrated Wildfire Risk Management (IWRM)** strategy is essential for Europe. Current approaches are often fragmented and reactive, focusing primarily on suppression, and prevention, rather than comprehensively integrating the evolving risk of wildfires in the European landscapes and societies. A unified strategy should encompass multi-agency cooperation, integrate diverse stakeholders, and leverage technological advancements to reduce wildfire risks holistically.

Key elements of this proposed strategy include establishing a dedicated EU-level agency to coordinate wildfire management efforts, harmonizing policies across member states, and the development of goals and targets

Figure 1: Countries involved in Green Deal Wildfire Risk Management research

including Key Performance indicators at multiple scales. By fostering collaboration, facilitating the spaces for multi-actor and cross-scale exchange of knowledge and good practices, and to improve interoperability for emergency response, Europe can better prepare for and mitigate the impacts of wildfires, ensuring the safety and resilience of its communities and ecosystems. Moreover, with the implementation of such a strategy, the EU can become a global leader and a reference model for other regions which are facing similar wildfire problems and are also moving into more integrated approaches.

The **European Union has invested about 70 Mio. € in wildfire risk research**, mainly under the Green Deal, addressing all aspects of wildfire risk management from prevention to response and recovery. The projects have developed a joint proposal for an [Integrated Wildfire Risk Management Strategy](#) depicting how **the latest research results** can contribute to **substantially reducing wildfire risk** if **mechanisms for scaling these solutions** are put in place. Importantly, research efforts have been made at a pan-European scale as the figure above depicts.

Key suggestion for Integrated Wildfire Risk Management

- European member states must shift their focus from suppression and prevention, **adopting a more holistic approach** to wildfire risk management. This requires a **collaborative effort among decision-makers, scientists, operational agents, the private sector**, and citizens to integrate urban planning, biodiversity, energy, and agricultural policies aimed at reducing wildfire risks. Emphasizing adaptation and rehabilitation strategies as **transformative opportunities** may enhance landscape resilience to climate and socio-economic changes.
- The development and implementation of a comprehensive **European Strategy** implemented by localized approaches at Member State and regional should be led by an **inter-agency working group** involving multiple EU directorates such as DG ECHO, DG ENV, and DG AGRI, among others. This group would coordinate efforts potentially establish a dedicated Wildfire Risk Management Agency.
- **Aligned national and regional initiatives** are essential to bring together relevant stakeholders for creating integrated strategies. Enabling permanent spaces that are not dependent on project-funding schemes and establishing **clear goals and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** will facilitate the monitoring and assessment of integrated wildfire risk management (IWRM) measures. A **better understanding of public expenditures** related to wildfire management is hence crucial for informed investment decisions. A **European legislative framework** could help to enforce these crucial aspects.
- The creation of a mechanism to facilitate the **sharing of data and exchange of good practice sharing and peer learning across Europe** for all aspect of Integrated Wildfire Management is crucial and should be **run by a dedicated organizational body or agency** at European level.
- A respective body should also create a **European Technical Working Group** to support the inter-agency working group on defining a work plan to implement the proposed strategy, suggest KPIs and contribute to the monitoring of the deployment of the strategy, and propose novel topics for future funding and investment based on bottom-up identified research needs and gaps.
- Enhance the **efficiency of pan-European response operations**, particularly through the Union Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM): Improve interoperability through harmonized protocols and common training as resources are exchanged during extended fire seasons at a pan-European level. Build capacity through investing in knowledge creation and sharing, particularly by enhancing the understanding of the upcoming risk of more intense, extreme and simultaneous wildfires across the different European realities.

Overall, a **mechanism**, that facilitates the **sharing of good practice, scaling of research results and application of risk reduction measures** including new technologies is needed. This should include the financing for adapting solutions to the diversity of local wildfire risk realities determined by vegetation and climate as well as socio-economic conditions. This mechanism should address all componets of Integrated Wildfire Risk Management as depicted in the figure below.

Figure 2: Components of Integrated Wildfire Risk Management